

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

**Deliverable: 3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated
Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)**

30/11/2020

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3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

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Disclaimer

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

This document reports on the 1st release of the Atmospheric Thematic services and the software underlying each service. This report, NEANIAS deliverable 3.4, comes out right after the first thematic atmospheric services release, deliverable D3.3.

The A1 Service, named “ATMO-FLUD”, (for flux densities) provides a set of algorithms for the calculation of flux densities of Sensible Heat, Latent Heat, Turbulent Kinetic Energy and other scalars like GHGs. The input data to the service is user provided although test data are available for trial runs. Real data should be experimentally obtained by the user bearing in mind that the fundamental method employed in this service is the “Eddy Covariance”.

The A2 Service comprises two services: one named “ATMO-STRESS” calculates the trajectories of tectonic stress based on a series of local data of stress and presents them as a map (stress field). The second service, named “ATMO-SEISM”, compares a series of parameters regarding the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere, in order to find possible correlations.

The A3 Service, named “ATMO-4CAST”, is responsible for Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting, providing users with the ability to obtain and visualise meteorological and air quality forecasts based on their own datasets through a central server. This is done by processing the incoming data, passing it through popular models such as WRF-ARW and CMAQ, and processing and creating visualisations based on their outputs.

For each *released* service a point-of-access is provided, as well as *interface* through which it may interact with other services and *documentation* explaining how to use it. Documentation of all NEANIAS atmospheric services is organized under NEANIAS docs service.

Services reported here have gone through the first release round, most services have been integrated to NEANIAS authentication system service, the documentation workflow, and integrated with GARR infrastructure services. As expected, this first milestone of services, uncovered some gaps in their deployment stack. Integration with other core and delivery services will be addressed for the next milestone and releases.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The NEANIAS WP3 “Atmospheric Thematic services” is focused on the co-design of four services in the atmospheric environment, addressing land-atmosphere interfaces, appropriate for the Research and Development user-communities. The atmospheric services will deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions and industrial stakeholders, e.g. engineering of air pollution control systems and related technology companies, and also end-users at national institutional level such as Civil Protection Agencies. Interest can arise also from more regional governmental institutions such as Regions and Municipalities, especially in relation to detection and evaluation of atmospheric anthropogenic or natural pollutants releases in the atmosphere. Conversely, the quantitation of their man made or natural sinks.

The first service A1, named FLUD, provides the users the ability to calculate atmospheric fluxes of Energy and Green House Gases across the terrestrial and oceanic interfaces, using the “Eddy Covariance” method and related algorithms (A1 ATMO-FLUD service). Explained in detail in the documentation that accompanies this service, are the fundamental scientific principles that support this method, the limitations that apply for these calculations and the format of the data input.

The A2 Service comprises two services: One named “ATMO-STRESS”, calculates the trajectories of tectonic stress based on a series of local data of stress, and presents them as a map (stress field). It permits the input of any data related to stress, spanning from earthquake focal mechanism solutions, to stress calculated from fault slip data sets, to geotechnical measurement of in-situ stresses. The second service, named “ATMO-SEISM”, compares a series of parameters regarding the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere, in order to find possible correlations. It automatically produces a series of graphs that correlate all the possible parameters, spanning from latitude and longitude of earthquakes, their foci, their depth, magnitude, distance from the point of gas measurement, gas concentrations, etc.

Finally, the A3 service, named “ATMO-4CAST” provides users the ability to obtain and visualise meteorological and air quality forecasts based on their own datasets. The service is hosted on a centralised server, which can receive different types of data, in GRIB or JSON formats, and the necessary model parameters and, passing them through popular models such as WRF-ARW and CMAQ, visualise the obtained outputs (e.g., a map with a visualisation of the forecasted air temperature). Such a service is useful for users who have their own datasets but do not have the required skills to build and run such complex software environments.

1.2. Content and Rationale

This deliverable, D3.4, is a report containing the details of the developed and validated Atmospheric Thematic Services delivered in the 1st release listed in the deliverable D3.3 “Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #1”.

Preliminary documents have been prepared for each of the Atmospheric services (A1, A2, A3), within the NEANIAS WP3 workspace, collecting the required datasets for service validation, software underlying technologies as well as collecting all possible contributions as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate their success.

The document reports, for each of the Atmospheric services, the main release components as identified in WP3 for their delivery and assessment; and their integration with core services provided by WP3. In particular, service documentation and service interface(s) exposing their functionalities in a customized way are reported and mainly provided by URLs. Furthermore, Service Validation addressed in “User Requirements”, as identified and reported in D3.1, are described.

NEANIAS Atmospheric services are built on top of TRL6 software – software fully functional in their original domain – and evolve the software towards TRL7 – in our context, fully operational in a cloud environment. The technology is already validated and the thematic service is creating prototypes in the context of the NEANIAS infrastructure, using cloud infrastructure and services provided by GARR and MEEO, and integrate relevant documentation, to be used as a test run for uncovering major obstacles across the NEANIAS collaboration. In the first release a minimal set of selected features are functional and stable, and documentation is complete to cover them, thus rendering the service usable by end users. In the next deliverables and milestones, services will go through cloud complete operation and stabilization (TRL7).

1.3. Structure of the document

This document is organized as follows. In chapter 2, we present a general overview of the NEANIAS Atmospheric services, the release processes and tools, and a summary of the released Atmospheric services. Chapter 3 provides short descriptions of each Atmospheric service released up to the date of this document. Chapter 4 reports the service validation and the user requirements fulfillment. Finally, in Chapter 5 we conclude this report with a summary of achievements, major issues and future steps.

This document is part of a series of documents to be released during NEANIAS development as the services develop and go through major releases. Each release milestone will get a separate report like this one. Until the next release this document may get updates, as often as needed, to reflect major improvements of Atmospheric services.

2. Release overview

2.1. General overview

The NEANIAS Atmospheric research services are aimed at supporting management and analysis of large data volumes in Atmospheric and Earth sciences via assisting the scientific community to establish fluxes of Energy and Green House gases across the terrestrial and oceanic interfaces, using the “Eddy Covariance” method and related algorithms (A1 ATMO-FLUD service), secondly, efficiently producing maps of stress affecting the Earth crust (A2 ATMO-STRESS service) and correlating huge amount of data of different parameters to understand the possible correlation between earthquakes and crustal gas emissions (A2 ATMO-SEISM), and finally, optimising, automating and validating software modules for air quality estimation along with the novel integrations of satellite, geospatial and in-situ data (A3 ATMO-4CAST).

2.2. Releases timeline

The Atmospheric Thematic services are released in three main cycles. Release #1 has been delivered in M12 (Deliverable D3.3 and the relative report in this document). The following table summarizes the Atmospheric services released and the main information related to the release.

Table 1 NEANIAS Atmospheric services released

Short name	Sector ¹	Lead ²	TRL ³	Version ⁴	Core Integration ⁵	Documentation Status ⁶	Testing Status ⁷	EOSC Registration Status ⁸
ATMO-FLUD	Atmospheric (A1)	ATHENA	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	complete	in progress	No
ATMO-STRESS	Atmospheric (A2)	NKUA	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	complete	in progress	No
ATMO-SEISM	Atmospheric (A2)	ATHENA	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	complete	in progress	No
ATMO-4CAST	Atmospheric (A3)	UBIWHERE	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	In progress	In progress	No

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The following table summarize the pre-release, testing and production project months and estimated exact dates.

Deliverable	Description	From project start			Exact dates		
		Production	Testing	Pre-release	Production	Testing	Pre-release
D3.3	Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #1	12	11	10	31/10/20	30/09/20	31/08/20
D3.5	Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #2	23	22	21	30/09/21	31/08/21	31/07/21
D3.7	Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #3	30	29	28	30/04/22	31/03/22	28/02/22

Table 2 Software development plan of the Atmospheric thematic service releases including estimated dates for pre-releases, testing and production.

Detailed plans for the 2nd release are reported in the next section for each service.

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3. Services

This chapter provides a tabular overview of each service: status, its endpoints and links to further information, introducing also the plans for the 2nd release.

3.1. A1 – Greenhouse gases flux density monitoring service

Service Status	The ATMO-FLUD service, using a set of algorithms is up and running, tested and ready for release. With the documentation and a questionnaire, a number of internal users have tried it and commented on the ease of use and the comprehension of the outputs.
Service Endpoints	https://atmo-flud.neanias.eu
Software information	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/a1-service/webapp https://gitlab.neanias.eu/a1-service/integration https://gitlab.neanias.eu/a1-service/scientific Documentation at: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service
Plans for 2nd release	Improvements based on feedback from end users but also GRADIENT FLUXES SERVICE is under preparation

3.2. A2 – Monitoring atmospheric perturbations and components in active tectonic regions service

Note that the A2 service has been implemented in **two separate instances/services**.

In particular, after the initial co-design sessions with the internal and external end-users from the Atmospheric community and based on the D3.1 outcome there was a requirement for two separate tools that able to handle the processing pipeline of the proposed A2 service. More specifically:

- ✓ the **first** one that has been implemented in the framework of NEANIAS is “**Atmo-STRESS**” that produces maps of tectonic stress trajectories based on a series of local stress data.
- ✓ the **second** one that has been implemented in the framework of NEANIAS is “**ATMO-SEISM**” service that targets end-users which are more experienced in scripting/programming, to help them explore and discover possible correlations between the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere.

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Service Status	A2 consists of service A2-1 ATMO-STRESS and service A2-2 ATMO-SEISM. The core functionalities of ATMO-STRESS were based on the LISSAGE software (Lee & Angelier, 1994). User authentication and authorization is handled by the NEANIAS AAI service (C2).
Service Endpoints	ATMO-STRESS Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service ATMO- STRESS: http://atmo-stress.neanias.eu
Software information	ATMO-STRESS Source Code: https://github.com/Olyna/Lissage https://gitlab.neanias.eu/a2-service/a2-1-service/a2-1-web-app https://gitlab.neanias.eu/a2-service/a2-1-service/a2-1-confs Current Release: 1.0.0
Plans for 2nd release	ATMO-STRESS: Improve functionality and usability based on user feedback by testing on various datasets. Integration with C4 core services for enhanced visualization.

Service Status	A2 consists of service A2-1 ATMO-STRESS and service A2-2 ATMO-SEISM. ATMO-SEISM has been developed as a Jupyter Notebook service hosted in a dedicated JupyterHub deployment. The ATMO-SEISM service, with the use of a developed Python Package (pyradon), enables users to comparingly process and analyze gas releases and earthquake datasets and plot useful visualizations.
Service Endpoints	ATMO-SEISM Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service ATMO-SEISM: http://atmo-seism.neanias.eu
Software information	ATMO-SEISM Source Code: https://github.com/alekfal/pyradon (private) https://gitlab.neanias.eu/a2-service/a2-2-service/a2-2-confs Current Release: 1.0.0
Plans for 2nd release	ATMO-SEISM: Improve functionality and usability based on user feedback by testing on various datasets. Integration with C3 core services for increased AI/ML functionalities and C4 core services for enhanced visualization.

3.3. A3 – Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting service

Service Status	ATMO-4CAST, the A3 service, is under development. Currently it is possible to input the GRIB and parameter files necessary to run the WRF-ARW model and obtain the output files, with generated visualisations in PDF files. These functionalities have been integrated and can be used through the NEANIAS portal. It has been integrated with NEANIAS AAI Service and is deployed in Ubiwhere’s cloud infrastructure. The components that adapt JSON input data and CMAQ are still under development/integration.
Service Endpoints	Documentation: - NEANIAS Instance: http://atmo-4cast.dev.neanias.eu/ NEANIAS Service Catalogue: http://catalogue.neanias.eu/service/Ubiwhere.air_quality_estimation_monitoring_and_forecasting
Software information	ATMO-4CAST Source Code: https://gitlab.ubiwhere.com/smart-cities-h2020/neanias (private) Current Release: 1.0.0
Plans for 2nd release	ATMO-4CAST: Improve functionality and usability based on user feedback and by allowing novel formats and means to submit data as input to the service (beyond GRIB). Moreover, the integration with NEANIAS Data Sharing Service is envisioned and, eventually, also in the Research Product Catalogue.

4. Atmospheric Services Validation and User Requirements fulfillments

Below, we provide information on service validation including data used to validate and assess service functionality and information about the user requirements addressed behind the service evolution and the software developed.

4.1. A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation and Addressed User Requirements

4.1.1. Entry to the service

The screenshot shows the NEANIAS Atmospheric Flux Densities service interface. On the left is a navigation menu with options: home, new study, past studies, documentation, my online storage (highlighted with a red box), and sign out. The main content area is titled "NEANIAS Atmospheric Flux Densities" and contains an "Input type selection" section. Below the title, it says "Please select input type for Eddy covariance execution." and lists three radio button options: "Demo file" (highlighted with a red box), "User file shared with this service", and "Direct upload". A "Next" button is located below the options.

Below the input selection, the interface displays "Execution parameters are displayed below" and a table:

Parameter	Value
Algorithm	Eddy covariance
Input type	Demo file
Input file	Demo/InputFastData_smaller.dat
Period	30 minutes
Limit	3.50
Angle from	30
Angle to	120

Below the table is a "Progress" section (highlighted with a red box) showing a progress bar for various steps: Initialize, Filtering, Despiking, Rotation, Creating Blocks, Footprint, Spectra, Plots, and Exporting. A "Show results" button (highlighted with a red box) is located at the bottom right of the progress section.

4.1.2. Some fundamentals

In micrometeorology, the eddy covariance method is used to determine turbulent fluxes across a boundary layer interface, as for example, the land-atmosphere or the sea-atmosphere interface. The method is theoretically simple in concept, provided that fast response sensors (determining atmospheric parameters and scalars at high frequency) are

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available. It can directly determine flux densities of energy, momentum and gases or aerosol, in a semi-continuous manner. However, in dealing with a “complex system” such as the atmosphere, nothing is simple. A number of assumptions have to be taken into account and a number of pre calculation and post calculation data treatment procedures have to be carried out.

Firstly, as the name indicates, the method determines the co variation of turbulent vertical motion of air and the vertical turbulent motion of energy, or momentum, or mass. In describing turbulent motion, one has to deconvolute the mean value of the motion from the fluctuation of the mean motion as can be described by the “Reynold’s deconvolution principle”. The turbulent motion of air at any instant can be defined as the mean value of its velocity vector (the vertical velocity in our case) plus the value of its fluctuation from the mean. Of course, the choice of the ensemble of values to calculate this mean is described later (in most of our cases it is 20-30 minutes as determined by the calculated ogives, *vide infra*). Hence, for example, in eddy covariance the product of the two means of the vertical wind velocity in one hand (w) and the mean of a mass concentration of a scalar (s) can be mathematically depicted as

$$F = \overline{w \cdot s} + \overline{w'} \cdot \overline{s'} = \overline{w \cdot s}$$

which means that the product of the two co-varying means is the mean of their products since the average of their variations are/or should always be zero (this is also a check for correctness of our calculations). Hence, the flux F of a scalar is defined as the mean of the product of the vertical wind velocity and the “value” of the scalar. The typical example here is:

Flux of CO₂ above a surface= mean of the vertical wind velocity in meters per second times the mean concentration of CO₂, in mg per cubic meter, resulting in a flux density of
mg. m⁻².s⁻¹

The convention here is that upward fluxes (from the interface) have a positive sign and downward fluxes (to the interface) have a negative sign. The flux density is conceptually the flow of mass from or to a unit area of the interface per unit time. In distinguishing the term “Flux density” from the term “Flux”, the latter is the flow of mass from a defined area for a specifically defined length of time, thus having units mass (flow) per area.

The assumptions for the above statistical calculations are numerous. The most important are discussed here. Flux calculations assume that the area under consideration has no horizontal gradient of the scalar, or otherwise, that there is a homogeneous horizontal concentration for the calculation of vertical flux. Secondly, that this assumption holds for the averaging period that we calculate flux density. Or again, otherwise, that there is no advection of scalar to this area. Thirdly, that the vertical wind velocity is determined at very high frequencies, together with scalar determination at the same high frequencies so that most of the turbulent transport can be captured. This means expensive ultrasonic anemometer(s) and even more expensive dedicated sensors are required. Fourthly, that the sensors determine mass per unit volume or that corrections involving the “ideal gas equation” are carried out within the instrument or offline. Other data pretreatment and post calculations corrections are listed below:

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- (I) Because of electronic and natural noise (e.g., insects interfere with the anemometer signal), data have to be “despiked”. This means that a datum peak, greater than 3 times the standard deviation of the mean ensemble value is deleted and replaced by the mean of its previous and next values. This is the simplest case.
- (II) Frequencies lower than the ones recorded and that appear in the time series, should be filtered out by a high pass filter. This means that only “high frequencies” of the co-spectra are considered because data of low frequency are due to large eddies and indicate advection. These large eddies should be filtered out. The high pass filter is initiated by the “block averaging” statistical treatment.
- (III) Planar rotation is a correction that may be needed to correct the leveling of the sonic anemometer to avoid vertical wind data contamination by horizontal wind.
- (IV) The cumulative sum of the co-varying frequencies indicates at what time this sum reaches a steady value, whereby this is considered as the optimum time for ensemble averaging of the co-spectra. Such a process is called the “ogives representation”.
- (V) The foot print of the area that is “sampled” by the instrumentation placed above the turbulent roughness layer, is calculated after the fetch (the length of the field away from the placed sensors) is calculated. Fetch and footprint are horizontal wind velocity and atmospheric stability depended.

4.1.3. Description of data input to the algorithm of eddy covariance flux densities calculations

The input file to the algorithm should have the following format:

- * Date-Time in the form: (2014-07-15 00:00:00)
 - * Ux (m/s): Horizontal wind velocity on the x axis, for the streamlines arriving at the directional sonic anemometer
 - * Uy (m/s): Vertical to x axis horizontal wind velocity
 - * Uz (m/s): Vertical to the interface wind velocity
 - * Sonic temperature Ts (°C): as measured by the sonic anemometer and calibrated, in situ, by a hot wire temperature sensor
 - * Wind Direction (deg): horizontal wind direction defined by the sonic anemometer
 - * Wind Speed (m/s): as determined by the sonic anemometer before deconvolution to Ux and Uy.
 - * Air Pressure (mbar): as measured by an in-situ barometer.
 - * In the present examples the water vapour concentration variations are used to calculate Latent Heat flux densities.
 - * Scalar concentration in units of mass per unit volume e.g. mg. m⁻³: as measured by the fast scalar sensor, it being of the open path (CORRECTIONS NEEDED), or of the closed path design.
- * All data should be separated by a comma.

An example of the ASCII file for the input of the 10Hz data is shown below:

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```

2014-07-15 00:00:00,2.708,1.843,-0.093,25.33,253.4,4.551,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.1,2.634,1.726,-0.149,25.35,253.4,4.36,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.2,2.715,1.777,-0.198,25.36,253.4,4.492,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.3,2.656,1.806,-0.225,25.38,253.4,4.462,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.4,2.666,1.872,-0.296,25.45,253.4,4.538,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.5,2.682,1.864,-0.293,25.33,253.4,4.546,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.6,2.656,1.82,-0.121,25.33,253.4,4.476,1010,0.00177525696271233

```

If one for the sake of understanding the input data, puts labels on each column of the 10Hz data, this is depicted below. The last column indicates the feasibility of the software to calculate flux densities of a number of scalars. However, data input should be entered as above.

	Time in tenths of second	Ux in m/s	Uy in m/s	Uz in m/s	Temp in Celsius	Wind direction- Degrees	Wind speed in m/s	Pressure in hPa	Water Vapour in mg/m ³	Other scalar [e.g. CO2 or CH4 in mg/m ³]
1	2014-07-15 00:00:00	2.708	1.843	-0.093	25.33	253.4	4.551	1010	0.00177525696	
2	2014-07-15 00:00:00.1	2.634	1.726	-0.149	25.35	253.4	4.36	1010	0.00177525696	
3	2014-07-15 00:00:00.2	2.715	1.777	-0.198	25.36	253.4	4.492	1010	0.00177525696	
4	2014-07-15 00:00:00.3	2.656	1.806	-0.225	25.38	253.4	4.462	1010	0.00177525696	
5	2014-07-15 00:00:00.4	2.666	1.872	-0.296	25.45	253.4	4.538	1010	0.00177525696	
6	2014-07-15 00:00:00.5	2.682	1.864	-0.293	25.33	253.4	4.546	1010	0.00177525696	
7	2014-07-15 00:00:00.6	2.656	1.82	-0.121	25.33	253.4	4.476	1010	0.00177525696	
8	2014-07-15 00:00:00.7	2.682	1.791	-0.125	25.28	253.4	4.473	1010	0.00177525696	
9	2014-07-15 00:00:00.8	2.738	1.847	-0.014	25.26	253.4	4.585	1010	0.00177525696	
10	2014-07-15 00:00:00.9	2.805	1.761	0.005	25.3	253.4	4.566	1010	0.00177525696	
11	2014-07-15 00:00:01	2.671	1.797	-0.108	25.41	253.5	4.488	1010	0.00177399327	
12	2014-07-15 00:00:01.1	2.658	1.836	-0.116	25.43	253.5	4.494	1010	0.00177399327	
13	2014-07-15 00:00:01.2	2.605	2.002	-0.123	25.44	253.5	4.607	1010	0.00177399327	
14	2014-07-15 00:00:01.3	2.693	2.015	-0.111	25.46	253.5	4.708	1010	0.00177399327	
15	2014-07-15 00:00:01.4	2.79	2.089	-0.109	25.46	253.5	4.879	1010	0.00177399327	
16	2014-07-15 00:00:01.5	2.789	2.106	-0.05	25.49	253.5	4.895	1010	0.00177399327	
17	2014-07-15 00:00:01.6	2.708	2.106	-0.098	25.43	253.5	4.814	1010	0.00177399327	
18	2014-07-15 00:00:01.7	2.648	2.046	-0.091	25.43	253.5	4.694	1010	0.00177399327	
19	2014-07-15 00:00:01.8	2.708	2.116	-0.101	25.41	253.5	4.824	1010	0.00177399327	
20	2014-07-15 00:00:01.9	2.8	2.155	-0.033	25.43	253.5	4.955	1010	0.00177399327	
21	2014-07-15 00:00:02	2.711	2.124	-0.117	25.46	250.6	4.835	1010	0.00177875815	
22	2014-07-15 00:00:02.1	2.481	2.161	-0.234	25.46	250.6	4.642	1010	0.00177875815	
23	2014-07-15 00:00:02.2	2.565	2.155	-0.192	25.41	250.6	4.72	1010	0.00177875815	
24	2014-07-15 00:00:02.3	2.589	2.098	-0.093	25.41	250.6	4.687	1010	0.00177875815	
25	2014-07-15 00:00:02.4	2.681	2.055	-0.131	25.45	250.6	4.736	1010	0.00177875815	
26	2014-07-15 00:00:02.5	2.673	1.956	-0.017	25.4	250.6	4.629	1010	0.00177875815	
27	2014-07-15 00:00:02.6	2.639	1.973	-0.14	25.43	250.6	4.612	1010	0.00177875815	
28	2014-07-15 00:00:02.7	2.604	1.885	-0.064	25.41	250.6	4.489	1010	0.00177875815	
29	2014-07-15 00:00:02.8	2.689	1.962	-0.053	25.4	250.6	4.651	1010	0.00177875815	

***IMPORTANT:**

1. When requested by the application, we insert numerical values in the following parameters:
 - a. Time period (default value in tenths of seconds: 18000 ==> Acceptable values: 3000 (5 minutes), 6000 (10 minutes), 9000 (15 minutes), 12000 (20 minutes), 15000 (25 minutes), 18000 (30 minutes). Time period depends on the values given by the ogive analysis.
 - b. Limit (default value): 3.5 times the standard deviation from the mean value of the ensemble. The ensemble is defined in point a. above.
 - c. Angle that the sonic faces the horizontal wind streamlines. For unidirectional ultrasonic anemometers this angle has to be user defined, with angle values up to 360 placed in both boxes. ***CAUTION: ONLY** for directional sonic anemometers an arc of 120 degrees should be considered. This means 60 degrees either side of the horizontal wind streamlines, whereby, the anemometer faces directly the streamlines. e.g., for wind coming from the north (0 degrees), arc should be from 300 degrees to 60 degrees. For wind coming from the southeast (135 degrees), arc should be from 75 degrees to 195 degrees. This means that for the first example the value of 300 should be placed in the first box and 60 in the second, etc. Values that are obtained

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beyond the 120 degrees horizontal wind streamlines arc may give erroneous results.

- d. For omnidirectional sonic anemometers values in both boxes should be the same and represent the horizontal wind direction streamlines.
2. NB: If we have a lot of empty values graphs 18 and 19 will not appear.

4.1.4. Outputs of a trial run

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Comparison of Raw Data and Despiked Data of H₂O Vapour Concentration for period=18000 and limit=0.5 from 15/7 to 15/7

Comparison of Raw Data and Despiked Data of Air Density for period=18000 and limit=0.5 from 15/7 to 15/7

Sonic data Despiked from large eddies

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4.1.5. Results in ascii file

```
Date,QH,QE,ustar,Bowen_ratio
2014-07-15 00:00:00.000,-11.206494695615659,4.600218301052997,0.13405899708455643,-
2.436078890658401
2014-07-15 00:30:00.000,-3.006180972151931,2.248388938550739,0.09610220407000725,-
1.3370377876390227
```

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2014-07-15 01:00:00.000,-2.610103269847478,-
1.1723241219074745,0.042586783068725834,2.226434840904417
2014-07-15 01:30:00.000,-1.4761490752857758,0.660222189050435,0.05398647850170871,-
2.2358368133746738
2014-07-15 02:00:00.000,-3.892844991248041,0.48793788823704015,0.04458379805780989,-
7.978156820970003
2014-07-15 02:30:00.000,-2.150765752586561,1.2479277068942487,0.060533507954558065,-
1.7234698297862379
2014-07-15 03:00:00.000,-1.262023972277743,-
0.9760476663069925,0.05985167541507122,1.2929942008393713
2014-07-15 03:30:00.000,-2.9739392863080583,-
0.4395642290232431,0.056528939553560066,6.76565354946297
2014-07-15 04:00:00.000,-6.768637465061029,-
0.3194221511997293,0.08866685916090133,21.190256967584926
2014-07-15
04:30:00.000,1.0920292182365736,-1.302099164833833,0.059995946216550224,-0.8386682425803819
2014-07-15
05:00:00.000,2.345924738232744,-0.8607817406346877,0.032359132454681354,-2.7253421250583254
2014-07-15
05:30:00.000,-2.0140394241540034,0.6776900793061451,0.06532242894966318,-2.971918116635385
2014-07-15

06:00:00.000,0.2193467228012514,-6.657747002730619,0.10954696037597635, 0.03294608862597034

2014-07-15
06:30:00.000,-4.105533436489474,9.065880446776562,0.10660833600266187,0.45285545740339267
2014-07-15
07:00:00.000,-0.8878329404267147,0.38511734184703045,0.07998654484323368,-2.305356949569319
2014-07-15
07:30:00.000,-7.104572272778737,5.378508497476185,0.12569934271871827,-1.3209186665992052
2014-07-15
08:00:00.000,9.488581257647697,19.10011878062786,0.26203029667951744,0.49678126961552793
2014-07-15
08:30:00.000,73.94928473097798,161.58130778270984,0.39373159219057585,0.45765989733430656
2014-07-15 08:59:55.600,8.377378605762733,44.44453121460238,0.3528546731763707,0.18849065063398218
2014-07-15
09:29:55.600,6.259301765235781,28.442472831624258,0.3387142305538349,0.22006883164800875
2014-07-15 09:59:55.600,99.64061623912863,82.11577877350858,0.43861863503836335,1.2134161999967996
2014-07-15 10:29:55.600,53.57856489130084,79.62212514041117,0.4688392472075262,0.6729105107005959
2014-07-15
10:59:55.600,128.69409303299145,109.88602880856504,0.5095465340992388,1.1711597409457062
2014-07-15 11:29:55.600,32.5741238440857,231.386518002069,0.36402643681413877,0.1407796807415732
2014-07-15 11:59:55.600,63.45402112959585,59.93622072365895,0.27635638055662054,1.0586923960747545

2014-07-15 12:29:55.600,37.866876046407356,417.80258595883134,0.38137041549950773,0.09063341711853026
2014-07-15 12:59:55.600,53.58702794129701,92.0841266342609,0.4997155509390777,0.5819355615342219
2014-07-15 13:29:55.600,41.12413503276831,168.43775186845733,0.4740048548037314,0.24415034383078502
2014-07-15 13:59:55.600,69.32367702032052,174.28092549853295,0.19352737680043067,0.3977697319544247
2014-07-15 14:29:55.600,42.66941581816208,107.01518086148614,0.27849901050940723,0.3987230173762986
2014-07-15
14:59:55.600,-0.2429409154454763,1.6970198275633316e-14,0.05380101697372106,-14315738184055.479
2014-07-15 15:29:55.600,,,,,
2014-07-15 15:59:55.600,,,,,
2014-07-15 16:29:55.600,,,,,
2014-07-15 16:59:55.600,,,,,
2014-07-15
17:29:55.600,-2.3068741344688757,-1.5932756615839998,0.3260697139615086,1.447881361707008
2014-07-15 17:59:55.600,202.42444627737785,294.8075400580872,0.6515465018995242,0.6866325272328289
2014-07-15
18:29:55.600,-7.929577699355302,-46.353511844778836,0.2212441679972055,0.17106746358093844

4.2. A2 ATMO-STRESS and ATMO-SEISM Validation and Addressed User Requirements

The A2 service has been implemented in two separate instances. The first “Atmo-STRESS” produces maps of tectonic stress trajectories based on a series of local stress data while in the second instance “ATMO-SEISM” service is directed to users which are more experienced in programming, to help them explore and discover possible correlations between the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere. This section discusses the validation of the two deployed services.

4.2.1. ATMO-STRESS

ATMO-STRESS Service has been tested by scientists, uploading as input files two different datasets regarding areas of about 4x4 to 30x30 km. Such datasets consist of field-collected data along the Northern Volcanic Zone of Iceland and seismological data from Yellowstone super volcano area (US). Data from Iceland focus on the opening direction of extension fractures where the azimuth is used as input directional data, together with Latitude and Longitude, expressed in Geographic coordinates (Datum WGS84), and elevation above the sea level; coordinates are derived from GPS instruments, whereas opening directions are measured using a compass. In regard to data from the Yellowstone area, they originate from focal mechanisms, where we used the T-axis as extensional direction. The azimuth of T-axes has been used as directional data to be processed.

In the present stage of the development, the service allows the calculation of Stress trajectory in a 2D space, where depth or elevation is not taken into account (up to now), using different methods for data interpolation: Polynomial or Distance Weight (Figure 1). Based on the type of interpolation chosen by the user, different parameters must be set, for example the Polynomial order of the equation. Output can be shown as Trajectory or grid, generated selecting “Compute maps” button, as well as it is possible to compute (Figure1) all combinations whose results are generated in a zipped file.

ATMO-STRESS service

Paleostress Trajectory Map Reconstruction

Select file to upload: Nessun file selezionato

List of available files:

Interpolation type:

Output:

Figure 1 – Screenshot of the online service in its present state, where it is possible to select two different methods for the interpolation processing

Figure 2 – Stress trajectories computed for the Yellowstone dataset using the polynomial method.

Figure 3 – Stress trajectories computed for Icelandic dataset using the polynomial method.

Even though this was service the 1st release of the software, it is possible to compute the stress trajectory for the selected input dataset. It is also possible to import the outputs in GIS. In fact, the output results are given in different formats: shapefiles which can be opened in GIS environments, KML which can be opened in Google Earth, and PNG and TIF image files.

The resulting maps can be used and analysed by scientists, the end-users. Some improvements regarding the graphical representation are recommended, as well as the necessity to add label axes. Furthermore, it must be possible to plot the trajectories in Google Earth. Finally, a check regarding the reliability between UTM and Geographic coordinates conversion, and vice versa, is under processing, to assure the right localization of the plotted trajectories.

4.2.2. ATMO-SEISM Service

The ATMO-SEISM Service has been tested by the end-users, uploading as input files two local datasets, both collected on Mt. Etna (Sicily, Italy): the first set contained gas radon emission measurements and meteorological parameters, measured by an installed probe, whereas the second set regarded earthquake parameters in the surrounding area (date/hour, magnitude, coordinates and depth). Regarding input files format, it is now possible to use only csv files, but not Excel files. The end users think that it would be useful to allow also the use of Excel file as inputs.

The software runs very well and all the graphs have been obtained automatically in a very short time. The various graphs combine in X- and Y-axes all the parameters that can be given to the service as data input. The resulting graphs have been analysed by the end-users, who think that minor corrections are required, affecting mostly the graphical aspect of the outputs. These requirements are presented hereunder, for the following graphs:

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1. Graph relating time, radon emissions and predicted radon: the unit of measurements of radon is missing on both the vertical axis and in the legend of the graph.

Figure 4 – Output graph of the ATMO-SEISM service, relating time with measured and predicted radon emissions.

2. Map showing the location of the earthquake hypocenters: a map representing only the area where earthquakes occurred must be displayed, or the possibility to zoom in this specific area must be added. Furthermore, the legend must be moved laterally and in a white square, because now it is not readable.

Figure 5 – Output map of the ATMO-SEISM service, showing the location of the earthquake hypocenters.

3. Graph relating longitude and depth of the hypocenters: dots must be scaled with the same size of the above presented map. Furthermore, it will be useful to add as new outputs two graphs, relating **latitude vs depth** and **magnitude vs depth**.

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Figure 6 – Output graph of the ATMO-SEISM service, relating hypocenters longitude with their depth.

- Graph relating time, radon and strain release: the unit of measurement of radon is missing, both along the axis and in the legend of the graph.

Figure 7 – Output graph of the ATMO-SEISM service, relating time, radon emission measurements and strain release due to seismic events.

- Graph relating time with filtered values of radon: the unit of measurement of radon is missing, both along the axis and in the legend of the graph.

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Figure 8 – Output graph of the ATMO-SEISM service, relating time and filtered radon emissions.

4.3. A3 ATMO-4CAST Validation and Addressed User Requirements

The Air quality forecasting service has been tested internally. For these tests, data from GFS (Global Forecasting Service¹) has been used. At the moment, only the WRF-ARW is being used (thus, returning meteorological forecasts), and the input data is in GRIB2 format. The service is outputting the normal WRF-ARW output files in netCDF format, but additionally it is also converting them to JSON to be processed externally. Finally, it is also producing PDF files with visualizations of the produced forecasts.

For the demo datasets, the service in general is taking around 15 minutes to run, but this time interval can vary immensely depending on the complexity of the simulation (timespan, grid size, etc.).

Below it is possible to find various menus that take the user from defining their simulation to their results, using NEANIAS interface (this interface might be improved in the future).

¹ <https://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/data-access/model-data/model-datasets/global-forecast-system-gfs>

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The screenshots illustrate the 'A3 Atmospheric Forecast' workflow in the NEANIAS system. The first screenshot shows the 'New atmospheric forecast' form, which includes fields for 'Forecast name', 'Forecast description', and file upload options for 'GRIB1 / GRIB2 Data', 'WPS Namelist configuration file', and 'WRF Namelist configuration file'. The second screenshot displays a table of forecasts:

Id	Name	Status
17	test	Finished
16	Test run	Finished

The third screenshot provides a detailed view of the forecast with Id 17, titled '17 - test'. It shows the forecast name 'test' and a list of output files:

Name	Size	Actions
plt_Precip.pdf	1.81 MB	Download
plt_Surface.pdf	912.70 KB	Download
wrfout_d01_2016-03-23_00:00:00	18.29 MB	Download
wrfout_d01_2016-03-23_00:00:00.json	25.99 MB	Download
wrfout_d01_2016-03-23_03:00:00	18.29 MB	Download
wrfout_d01_2016-03-23_03:00:00.json	30.04 MB	Download
wrfout_d01_2016-03-23_06:00:00	18.29 MB	Download

Below is an example of the output of the model, representing on a map the forecasted surface temperature, sea level pressure and wind direction and speed (using wind barsbs representation²). The forecast is for the area around the central United States.

² [http://ww2010.atmos.uiuc.edu/\(Gh\)/guides/maps/sfcobs/wnd.rxml](http://ww2010.atmos.uiuc.edu/(Gh)/guides/maps/sfcobs/wnd.rxml)

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WRF

Init: 2016-03-23_00:00:00
Valid: 2016-03-24_00:00:00

Surface Temperature (C)
Sea Level Pressure (hPa)
Wind (m/s)

Sea Level Pressure Contours: 900 to 1100 by 4

The following image is just representing the forecasted precipitation:

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WRF

Init: 2016-03-23_00:00:00
Valid: 2016-03-24_00:00:00

5. Service Validation Summary

Overall, the first release of WP3 services managed to fulfil the end-user requirements. In particular, the deployed Atmospheric services were compared against the table contained in D3.1, chapter 3 (**Co-design and Service Specifications**). We therefore keep track of the implementation of the most prominent user requirements assessed in the earlier stages of the project according to table 3 below.

Regarding the service assessment performed by the end-users, all NEANIAS internal end-users thoroughly evaluated the first release of all WP3 services. In particular, ATHENA, UBIWHERE, MEEO NOA and UNIMIB (Geology) validated the four WP3 services and their comments and experience was marked down in specially prepared Test Log files which are all attached in the Appendix. Moreover, different researchers and personnel, from the internal end-users institutes/SMEs with different background and expertise evaluated the services in order to assess the services in terms of the level of experience, technical or thematic expertise required for using smoothly and operationally the deployed in WP3 services. Based also on the specific application domain of each end-user, more emphasis was given on specific services that are addressing domain-related challenges.

As stated in Section 4 the A2 service has been implemented in two separate instances. The first “Atmo-STRESS” produces maps of tectonic stress trajectories based on a series of local stress data while the second instance “ATMO-SEISM” targets users more experienced in programming to help them explore and discover possible correlations between the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere.

Requirement				Specifications			1 st Release Validated Status for WP3 Service			
Req#	Requirement	Priority	Value	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Atmo-FLUD (A1)	Atmo-STRESS (A2-1)	Atmo-SEISM (A2-2)	Atmo-4CAST (A3)
R00	Common AAI	High	High	S00	Common SSO for all NEANIAS services	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
R01	Upload, store and possibly publish datasets of various formats	High	High	S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for uploading / downloading data to medium / long storage locations through well-known protocols (FTP, WebDAV, etc.) and make data FAIR when applicable	A1, A2, A3	Y	Integration with DaShaS has been completed. Data publishing is not	Service specific per user storage space	Y
R02	Use datasets provided by the services	Low	Medium	S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for accessing data made available by the service provider for testing and learning the functionalities of the service	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	partly
R03	Visualize raw data, resulting products and reports	Medium	High	S02	Each Atmospheric service implements task-specific reporting mechanisms	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
				S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing raw data and results	A1, A2, A3	Y	N	N	N
R04	To access data from suitable on-line repositories and data sources	Medium	High	S04	Implement task-specific services for accessing data provided through custom APIs	A1, A2, A3	Currently not applicable	Currently not applicable	Currently not applicable	Currently not applicable
				S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for accessing data made available by external repositories when provided through standard data protocols	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	N
R05	Document the workflow	Medium	Medium	S05	Atmospheric services implement suitable logging mechanisms and store meta-data describing the service parametrization	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	partly	Y
				S06	Interface with AAI, auditing and other relevant NEANIAS services for collecting user-related information	A1, A2, A3	Y	partly	partly	partly
				S01	Interface with NEANIAS data transfer and other relevant services for storing and publishing logs and the workflow related meta-data	A1, A2, A3	Y	partly	partly	Y
R06	Export the results in various file formats	Low	Medium	S07	Each service offers option to serialize the produced data in widely used file formats	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	partly	Y

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Req#	Requirement	Priority	Value	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Atmo-FLUD (A1)	Atmo-STRESS (A2-1)	Atmo-SEISM (A2-2)	Atmo-4CAST (A3)
				S01	Interfaces with NEANIAS data transfer services for storing the output data on suitable storage locations	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	partly	N
Requirement				Specifications			1 st Release Validated Status for WP3 Service			
Req#	Requirement	Priority	Value	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Atmo-FLUD (A1)	Atmo-STRESS (A2-1)	Atmo-SEISM (A2-2)	Atmo-4CAST (A3)
R07	Correlate gas emissions (e.g. Radon) with earthquake events and atmospheric conditions in active tectonic regions	High	High	S08	Compute correlation and other statistical quantities of interest between a set of relevant variables defined by the user	A2	-	-	Y	-
				S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for accessing data through standard data transfer protocols	A2	-	-	Y	-
				S04	Interface with task-specific services for accessing data through custom APIs	A2	-	-	Y	-
R08	Produce maps of the regional stress field of a study area which are compatible with GIS environments	High	High	S09	Compute stress field maps based on well-known interpolation methods (e.g. inverse distance weighting or bivariate polynomial function)	A2	-	Y	-	-
				S07	Support export to data formats compatible with GIS environments (e.g. geoTIFF, KML, geoJSON, etc.)	A2	-	Y	-	-
				S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for storing data using standard data transfer protocols	A2	-	Y	-	-
R09	Aggregate, harmonise and store cross-domain data from multiple sources (satellite, geospatial, in-situ) for air quality monitoring	High	High	S10	Integrate Smart Air Quality's management platform as a SaaS platform	A3	-	-	-	N
				S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for accessing and storing data through standard data transfer protocols	A3	-	-	-	Y
				S04	Interface with task-specific services for accessing data through custom APIs	A3	-	-	-	Currently not applicable
R10	Aggregate, harmonise and store GHG flux related	High	High	S11	Aggregate and harmonize cross-domain GHG flux data	A1, A3	Y	-	-	N

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	data on a regional / national scale			S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for accessing and storing data through standard data transfer protocols	A1, A3	Y	-	-	N
				S04	Interface with task-specific services for accessing data through custom APIs	A1, A3	Y	-	-	Currently not applicable
Requirement				Specifications			1 st Release Validated Status for WP3 Service			
Req#	Requirement	Priority	Value	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Atmo-FLUD (A1)	Atmo-STRESS (A2-1)	Atmo-SEISM (A2-2)	Atmo-4CAST (A3)
R11	Calculate the flux densities of GHG emissions	High	High	S12	Compute flux densities of GHG emissions (dynamic gradient calculations, eddy covariance)	A1	Y	-	-	-
R12	Filter the GHG emissions and energy fluxes per area or location	Medium	High	S14	EOSC service is able to filter data with geographies as input parameters	A3	Y	-	-	N
R13	To upload their own measurements for computing flux densities	High	High	S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for storing user-provided data using standard data transfer protocols	A1	Y	-	-	-
R14	To employ available atmospheric data from NEANIAS for flux densities	Medium	High	S13	Define default parametrization and example scenarios for testing / learning each provided service	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
R15	To compare their own software with the NEANIAS developed one	High	High	S02	Each service reports suitable evaluation metrics which allow for comparison with other related methods / software	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
				S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for uploading user reference results for comparison	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	partly	partly
R16	Improve portability and reproducibility	Medium	High	S05	Atmospheric services implement suitable logging mechanisms and store meta-data describing the service parametrization	A1, A2, A3	Y	partly	partly	Y
				S01	Interface with NEANIAS data transfer and other relevant services for storing and publishing logs and the workflow related meta-data	A1, A2, A3	Y	partly	partly	Y

5.1. Atmo-FLUD end-user evaluation summary

The feedback from users validating the first release of the service has generally been very positive. The service has been tested with a range of parameters available to the users and ten (10) test “real data” input files. The main comments from the users include indications of typos/minor errors to be corrected on the web pages displayed by the service, and problems with uploading the particular input file(s) provided for testing. This feedback will be taken into account in the next releases of the service, including making the appropriate revisions to improve user experience and understanding of how to use the service.

5.2. Atmo-STRESS end-user evaluation summary

The users that have validated the first release of the service have in general expressed their satisfaction on the basic functionalities offered by the service as well as its user interface and the compatibility of the service products with standard GIS environments and pipelines. The service has been thoroughly tested considering datasets which span a wide range of scales and locations. At the same time, the users proposed a series of improvements targeting mainly the graphical representations provided and the information contained in the plots. These recommendations will be taken into account to improve user experience in subsequent releases of the service.

5.3. Atmo-SEISM end-user evaluation summary

The users have tested the service by adapting the sample Jupyter notebook provided, introducing additional datasets besides the ones bundled with the service. Being the service implemented as a highly customisable Jupyter notebook powered by task-specific developed libraries, user feedback can be distinguished into two main categories. The first category regards feedback from users who are familiar with the read-eval-print loop (REPL) and other relevant programming environments. Feedback from this group of users states that the service can handle data files formatted in different ways, while supporting different forms of well-known tabular data files, as csv and xlsx. In particular, support of xlsx files has been added based on preliminary user feedback. In their feedback, the users have also indicated a number of improvements that can be applied to the plots and graphs produced by the service. These recommendations will be taken into account to improve subsequent versions of the service. The second feedback category comes from users who are less familiar with REPL environments. These users have found it very difficult to use the service and get results. This concern will be thoroughly examined, as to allow the use of the service functionalities also through an interface friendlier to a broader audience.

5.4. Atmo-4CAST end-user evaluation summary

The users have tested the service and the feedback is positive. Most remarks are regarding UI components layout, responsiveness and feedback. For example, they have suggested that more information should be accompanying the status code of a study; that they had some difficulty in understanding that multiple files could be uploaded; and having a choice field with only one input option available caused some confusion, but there are plans to add more in

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448.

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the future. Some users noted the example took a while to complete, this is, however, part of the nature of the service. We hope that providing more information to the user during runtime (e.g., the status of the process) will mitigate this. The recommendations provided by the test users will be taken into account to improve subsequent versions of the service.

6. Summary and future steps

We successfully improved the four services belonging to the Atmospheric Thematic services. The Atmospheric Thematic services are:

A1 - "ATMO-FLUD" (for flux densities) that provides a set of algorithms for the calculation of flux densities of Sensible Heat, Latent Heat, Turbulent Kinetic Energy and other scalars like GHGs. The input data to the service is user provided although test "real data" are available for trial runs;

A2 - "ATMO-STRESS" that comprises two services that analyse the conditions that guide the uprising of gas through the Earth crust and its release in the atmosphere; these services are "ATMO-STRESS" that calculates the trajectories of tectonic stress based on a series of local data of stress, and presents them as a map (stress field), and "ATMO-SEISM" that compares a series of parameters regarding the seismicity of a region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere, in order to find possible correlations;

A3 - "ATMO-4CAST" that is responsible for Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting, providing users with the ability to obtain and visualise meteorological and air quality forecasts based on their own datasets through a central server. This is done by processing the incoming data, passing it through popular models such as WRF-ARW and CMAQ, and processing and creating visualisations based on their outputs.

For each released service a point-of-access is provided, as well as an interface through which it interacts with other services and documentation explaining how to use it. Documentation of all NEANIAS atmospheric services is organized under NEANIAS docs service.

Services reported here have gone through the first release round. Most services have been integrated to NEANIAS authentication system service, the documentation workflow, and have been integrated with GARR infrastructure services. As expected, this first milestone of services uncovered some gaps in the services deployment stack. Integration with other core and delivery services will be addressed for the next milestones and releases.

Each service has been tested and validated, and a series of suggestions were defined in order to improve the services and the User Interface in the future steps of development.

No issues or deviations from original plans arose at this step.

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ARW	Advanced Research WRF
CMAQ	Community Multiscale Air Quality
GARR	Gruppo per l'Armonizzazione delle Reti della Ricerca
GFS	Global Forecasting Service
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Position System
GRIB	General Regularly-distributed Information in Binary form
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MEEO	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
netCDF	Network Common Data Form
WRF	Weather Research and Forecasting

Appendix 1

List of number of end users for each service internally inside NEANIAS and the User Board.
And category (Academic/Research/SMEs)

Atmospheric Services	Number of Users	Category	Involved Projects
A1 ATMO-FLUD	12	Academics & Researchers	
A2 ATMO-STRESS	7	Academy	
A2 ATMO-SEISM	5	Academy	
A3 ATMO-4CAST	6	Researcher	
sum	30		

Appendix 2

Forms compiled by developers and testers of the various services.

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NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Mema (Dimitra-Isidora) Roussopoulou
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	07/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0001		
Description	Running flux densities with direct upload		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	<p>There is a typo on the screen labelled "Execution validation". Check the sentence: "Please validate your selection before submitting you request." The word "you" must be changed to "your". I would also reword "validate" to simply "check" in that same sentence.</p> <p>On the same web page, I would place a space between the word "Uploads" and the file pathname.</p>		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Mema Roussopoulou
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	08/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	No further comments.		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Eleni Petra
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	08/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Fail	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	No success in the uploading process of data either by a) sharing b) uploading by the service 'input file uploading' option		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Dimitra Karali
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	08/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	the data should be saved through the browser (fileàsave as). If saved in different way (ctrl+A and copy paste in new txt file) the run cannot be completed.
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	Fast running (0:01:09.738436)		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Bodare Phillip
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	08/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	Fast execution
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	Smooth navigation and scrolling
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	<Optionally provide general comments for service>		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Alex Stavridis
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	09/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0001		
Description	Running flux densities with direct upload		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	Immediate response and sophisticated dialogue framework		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Athanasios Argiriou
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	07/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0001		
Description	Running flux densities with direct upload		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	The whole procedure was very fast and user friendly. The graphics are of very good quality.		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Effie Zafeirakopoulou
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	07/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments			

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NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	K. Kourtidis
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	10/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	The link to the data file (20140402.dat) you have sent me led me directly to the open file. Hence, I had to copy and paste the contents to notepad and save it as txt, since I could not download the file.
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	a. Fail b. Pass	a) With 10 min period and angle 150-210, the progress monitoring seems to have stopped at the filtering step, as far as I can tell. After waiting 25 minutes I aborted the service at this point. b) I started again with 30 min period and predefined angle 180-310 and it was executed.
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	H2O vapour concentration is in mg/m3, should be g/m3.
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	<Optionally provide general comments for service>		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Zoi Panagiota Kryona zoipkryo@gmail.com
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	07/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	The filtering progress bar wasn't full.		

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Michalis Konstantopoulos
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	09/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0001		
Description	Running flux densities with direct upload		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments			

NEANIAS A1 ATMO-FLUD Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS ATMO-FLUD	Validation Designed by:	S. RAPSOMANIKIS rapso@athenarc.gr
Module Name:	ATMO-FLUD	Designed date:	26th November 2020
Release Version:	1.0.0	Validation Executed by:	Rea Loupa
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	06/12/2020
Requirements	Availability of test data (ensured by validation designer)		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-flud.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service		

Use Case#	UC-ATMO-FLUD-0002		
Description	Running flux densities with upload via Nextcloud		
Preconditions	available data should be uploaded only by user		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged on	Pass	
Send data to service	Data submitted	Pass	
Submit execution parameters	Algorithm started execution	Pass	
Monitor algorithm execution	Algorithm finished	Pass	
View result in the browser	UI task	Pass	
Download results	File downloaded to user's computer	Pass	
Use case result	Pass		
General comments	The easiest to run and execute tool that I have found free in the web. The whole procedure lasted approximately 20 min.		

TABULATED RESULTS OF TRIALS for ATMO-FLUD

TESTER	GENERAL COMMENTS	SPECIFIC COMMENTS
MEMA 1	There is a typo on the screen labelled "Execution validation". Check the sentence: "Please validate your selection before submitting you request." The word "you" must be changed to "your". I would also reword "validate" to simply "check" in that same sentence.	

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	On the same web page, I would place a space between the word "Uploads" and the file pathname.	
MEMA 2	No further comments.	
EP	No success in the uploading process of data either by a) sharing b) uploading by the service 'input file uploading' option	
DK	Fast running (0:01:09.738436)	The data should be saved through the browser (fileàsave as). If saved in different way (ctrl+A and copy paste in new txt file) the run cannot be completed
Ph.B		Fast execution Smooth navigation and scrolling
AS	Immediate response and sophisticated dialogue framework	
AA	The whole procedure was very fast and user friendly. Graphs are of very good quality.	
EZ		
KK	H2O vapour concentration is in mg/m3, should be g/m3.	The link to the data file (20140402.dat) you have sent me lead directly to the open file. Hence, I had to copy and paste the contents to notepad and save it as txt, since I could not download the file. a) With 10 min period and angle 150-210, the progress monitoring seems to have stopped at the filtering step, as far as I can tell. After waiting 25 minutes I aborted the service at this point. b) I started again with 30 min period and predefined angle 180-310 and it executed.
Z-PK	The filtering progress bar was not full.	
MK		
RL	The easiest to run and execute tool that I have found free in the web. The whole procedure lasted 20 min approximately.	

NEANIAS A2.1 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Fabio Luca Bonali Fabio.bonali@unimib.it
Dependencies:	<LIST- DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	01/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0010		
Test Description	Uploading of a data set related to the north Iceland stress field		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Upload -or choose an existing- file	Results correspond to selected/uploaded file	OK	Ok for both uploading and choosing an existing file
2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method	Results correspond to selected interpolation method	OK	
3 Select "Order" parameter	Results correspond to selected order value	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values	Results correspond to selected input value or parameters are automatically defined if left empty	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
5 Select "Output type"	Results correspond to selected output type	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods

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6 Compute maps	Results appear at the bottom of the page after the required processing time	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
7 Download result	User downloads a .zip file containing the results in three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and a report (.json)	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
Test result	Uploading of dataset and plotting of maps have been completed successfully, and also the downloading of the results.		

NEANIAS A2.1 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Fabio Luca Bonali Fabio.bonali@unimib.it
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	30/11/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0020		
Test Description	Uploading of a data set related to Mt.Etna (NE Rift) stress field		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Upload -or choose an existing- file	Results correspond to selected/uploaded file	OK	Ok for both uploading and choosing an existing file

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method	Results correspond to selected interpolation method	OK	Both work BUT it is needed to refresh the page to run a new processing
3 Select "Order" parameter	Results correspond to selected order value	OK	It works both with "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, but it is needed to refresh the page to run a new processing with little changing of the parameter (e.g. Order from 0 to 1 or 2).
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values	Results correspond to selected input value or parameters are automatically defined if left empty	OK	They work in AUTO mode.
5 Select "Output type"	Results correspond to selected output type	OK	Works for both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
6 Compute maps	Results appear at the bottom of the page after the required processing time	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
7 Download result	User downloads a .zip file containing the results in three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and a report (.json)	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
Test result	I have tested 4 large datasets from the World Stress Map Project: uploading, processing, data plot and download work for all tested dataset, characterised by n. 461-5416 records.		

NEANIAS A2.1 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Noemi Corti n.corti3@campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	<LIST- DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	20/11/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0010		
Test Description	Uploading of a data set related to the north Iceland stress field		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Upload -or choose an existing- file	Results correspond to selected/uploaded file	OK	Ok for both uploading and choosing an existing file. The same dataset, has been tested twice, with a different field order.
2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method	Results correspond to selected interpolation method	OK	
3 Select "Order" parameter	Results correspond to selected order value	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values	Results correspond to selected input value or parameters are automatically defined if left empty	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

5 Select "Output type"	Results correspond to selected output type	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
6 Compute maps	Results appear at the bottom of the page after the required processing time	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
7 Download result	User downloads a .zip file containing the results in three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and a report (.json)	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
Test result	Uploading of dataset (number of records = 1633) and plotting of maps have been completed successfully, and also the downloading of the results. The service works independently of the field order in the input file.		

NEANIAS A2.1 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Noemi Corti n.corti3@campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	30/11/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0020		
Test Description	Uploading of a data set related to Mt.Etna (NE Rift) stress field		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

1 Upload -or choose an existing- file	Results correspond to selected/uploaded file	OK	Ok for both uploading and choosing an existing file. The same dataset, has been tested twice, with a different field order.
2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method	Results correspond to selected interpolation method	OK	
3 Select "Order" parameter	Results correspond to selected order value	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values	Results correspond to selected input value or parameters are automatically defined if left empty	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
5 Select "Output type"	Results correspond to selected output type	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
6 Compute maps	Results appear at the bottom of the page after the required processing time	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
7 Download result	User downloads a .zip file containing the results in three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and a report (.json)	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
Test result	Uploading of dataset (number of records = 153) and plotting of maps have been completed successfully, and also the downloading of the results. The service works independently of the field order in the input file.		

NEANIAS A2.1 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Noemi Corti n.corti3@campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	<LIST- DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	04/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0020		
Test Description	Uploading of a data set related to World Stress Map project		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Upload -or choose an existing- file	Results correspond to selected/uploaded file	OK	Ok for both uploading and choosing an existing file. The same dataset, has been tested twice, with a different field order.
2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method	Results correspond to selected interpolation method	OK	
3 Select "Order" parameter	Results correspond to selected order value	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values	Results correspond to selected input value or parameters are automatically defined if left empty	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

5 Select "Output type"	Results correspond to selected output type	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
6 Compute maps	Results appear at the bottom of the page after the required processing time	Fail	Maps are computing correctly for "polynomial" interpolation (both output types), and for "Distance Weighted" interpolation only if I choose the "Grid" output type, BUT maps are not computing if I choose "Distance Weighted" interpolation AND "Trajectories" output type simultaneously. In this latter case, the service continues to run without computing a map.
7 Download result	User downloads a .zip file containing the results in three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and a report (.json)	OK	If maps are computed correctly (see step 6), it is possible to download the results.
Test result	Uploading of dataset (number of records = 461) has been completed successfully, and also the selection of all the options is possible. Maps are computed correctly, EXCEPT for the case when "Distance Weighted" interpolation and the "Trajectories" output mode are selected simultaneously. The service works independently of the field order in the input file.		

NEANIAS A2.1 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Alessandro Tibaldi Alessandro.tibaldi@unimib.it
Dependencies:	<LIST- DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	29/11/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0010		
Test Description	Uploading of a data set related to the north Iceland stress field		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Upload -or choose an existing- file	Results correspond to selected/uploaded file	OK	Ok for both uploading and choosing an existing file
2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method	Results correspond to selected interpolation method	OK	Selection works
3 Select "Order" parameter	Results correspond to selected order value	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values	Results correspond to selected input value or parameters are automatically defined if left empty	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
5 Select "Output type"	Results correspond to selected output type	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

6 Compute maps	Results appear at the bottom of the page after the required processing time	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
7 Download result	User downloads a .zip file containing the results in three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and a report (.json)	OK	For both "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
Test result	Uploading of dataset and plotting of graphic outputs and results have been successful.		

NEANIAS A2.1 ATMO-STRESS Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Olympia Gounari olympia_g@live.com Makis Ntouskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-STRESS	Software Designed date:	11/2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Elena Russo e.russo11@campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	26/11/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access: required Input file: .txt format Restrictions: field separator = comma, decimal point = dot Input dataset should contain the following fields: 1) Point geographic coordinates in WGS'84 (epsg:4326) Coordinate Reference System 2) Azimuth of horizontal stress axis direction for each point (0-360 degrees) Input dataset field names should be "Lat" for latitude, "Lon" for longitude and "Azimuth" for azimuth angle.		
Service access/download	Service: https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/ Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-STRESS-0010		
Test Description	Uploading of a data set related to the north Iceland stress field		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Upload -or- choose an existing- file	Results correspond to selected/uploaded file	OK	OK uploading and choosing existing file
2 Select "Polynomial" or "Distance Weighted" method	Results correspond to selected interpolation method	OK	OK, it is possible to make the selection

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

3 Select "Order" parameter	Results correspond to selected order value	OK	For "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
4 Optional. Set "k", "p", "R" values	Results correspond to selected input value or parameters are automatically defined if left empty	OK	For "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
5 Select "Output type"	Results correspond to selected output type	OK	For "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods
6 Compute maps	Results appear at the bottom of the page after the required processing time	OK	For "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
7 Download result	User downloads a .zip file containing the results in three file formats (.shp, .kml, .geotiff) compatible with GIS environments, result's quick preview (.png) and a report (.json)	OK	For "Polynomial" and "Distance Weighted" methods, and for both output types
Test result	OK for uploading of dataset and plotting of maps, as well as for results download.		

NEANIAS A2.2 ATMO-SEISM Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Alekos Falagas alek.falagas@gmail.com , Makis Douskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-SEISM	Software Designed date:	11-2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Noemi Corti n.corti3@campus.campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	-	Date of Execution:	20/11/2020
Test Requirements	internet access		
Service access/download	Service: http://atmo-seism.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0010		
Test Description	Login and uploading of a data set related to radon measurements and earthquake data		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Open Service and login	A successful login with NEANIAS SSO Identity provider to the service	OK	
2 Upload data to Jupyter Hub	Data successfully uploaded to the server	OK	
Test result	Login and uploading of datasets related to earthquake data and gas measurements have been concluded successfully, both csv and Excel files		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0011		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (.csv files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console	OK	
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined	OK	

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

Test result	Uploading of data in the notebook and plotting of a series of graphs have been completed successfully, even if some improvements must be done (listed in the paragraph 4.2)		
Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0012		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (xlsx files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console	OK	
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined	Fail	Errors appear for plots considering the field "Date/Hour" both of the gas and of the earthquake dataset; the others are OK
Test result	Uploading of data from .xlsx files in the notebook has been completed successfully, but errors appear for graphs where the field "Date/Hour" of both gas and earthquake files are considered. The other graphs (earthquake plotting etc.) are OK, so probably there is an error in the two imported datasets, especially in the "Date/Hour" fields		

NEANIAS A2.2 ATMO-SEISM Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Alekos Falagas alek.falagas@gmail.com , Makis Douskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-SEISM	Software Designed date:	11-2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Noemi Corti n.corti3@campus.campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	-	Date of Execution:	20/11/2020
Test Requirements	internet access		
Service access/download	Service: http://atmo-seism.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0020		
Test Description	Login and uploading of a data set related to SO2 measurements and earthquake data		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Open Service and login	A successful login with NEANIAS SSO Identity provider to the service	OK	
2 Upload data to Jupyter Hub	Data successfully uploaded to the server	OK	
Test result	Login and uploading of datasets related to earthquake data and gas measurements have been concluded successfully, both csv and Excel files		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0021		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (.csv files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console	OK	

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined	OK	
Test result	Uploading of data in the notebook and plotting of a series of graphs have been completed successfully, even if some improvements must be done (listed in the paragraph 4.2). We noticed that, due to the fact that this dataset is not a continuous time series, and to the small amount of data, the resulting plots are not scientifically useful.		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0022		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (xlsx files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console	OK	
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined	OK	
Test result	Uploading of data from .xlsx files in the notebook has been completed successfully, even if some improvements must be done (listed in the paragraph 4.2). We noticed that, due to the fact that this dataset is not a continuous time series, and to the small amount of data, the resulting plots are not scientifically useful.		

NEANIAS A2.2 ATMO-SEISM Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Alekos Falagas alek.falagas@gmail.com , Makis Douskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-SEISM	Software Designed date:	11-2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Noemi Corti n.corti3@campus.campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	-	Date of Execution:	01/12/2020
Test Requirements	internet access		
Service access/download	Service: http://atmo-seism.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0030		
Test Description	Login and uploading of a second dataset related to radiant flux and earthquake data		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Open Service and login	A successful login with NEANIAS SSO Identity provider to the service	OK	
2 Upload data to Jupyter Hub	Data successfully uploaded to the server	OK	Both .csv and .xlsx files have been uploaded
Test result	Login and uploading of datasets related to earthquake data and gas measurements have been concluded successfully, both csv and Excel files		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0031		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (csv files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console	OK	

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined	Fail	Errors appear for plots considering the field "Date/Hour" of the gas dataset; the others are OK
Test result	Uploading of data from .csv files in the notebook has been completed successfully, but errors appear for graphs where the field "Date/Hour" of the gas file is considered. The other graphs (earthquake plotting etc.) are OK, so probably there is an error in the imported gas dataset, especially in the "Date/Hour" field		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0032		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (xlsx files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated	OK	Both for gas measurements and earthquake data
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console	OK	
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined	Fail	Errors appear for plots considering the field "Date/Hour" both of the gas and of the earthquake dataset; the others are OK
Test result	Uploading of data from .xlsx files in the notebook has been completed successfully, but errors appear for graphs where the field "Date/Hour" of both gas and earthquake files are considered. The other graphs (earthquake plotting etc.) are OK, so probably there is an error in the two imported datasets, especially in the "Date/Hour" fields		

NEANIAS A2.2 ATMO-SEISM Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Alekos Falagas alek.falagas@gmail.com , Makis Douskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-SEISM	Software Designed date:	11-2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Alessandro Tibaldi Alessandro.tibaldi@unimib.it
Dependencies:	-	Date of Execution:	29/11/2020
Test Requirements	internet access		
Service access/download	Service: http://atmo-seism.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0010		
Test Description	Login and uploading of a data set related to radon measurements and earthquake data		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Open Service and login	A successful login with NEANIAS SSO Identity provider to the service	OK	
2 Upload data to Jupyter Hub	Data successfully uploaded to the server	OK	
Test result	Login and uploading of datasets related to earthquake data and gas measurements have been concluded successfully, both csv and Excel files		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0011		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (.csv files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	Fail	Procedure too complicated and not friendly at all.
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes		
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated		
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console		
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined		

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

Test result	The step 1 Import python packages follows a procedure too complicate for not skilled people on these issues.		
Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0012		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (xlsx files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	Fail	Procedure too complicate and not friendly at all.
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes		
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated		
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console		
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined		
Test result	The step 1 Import python packages follows a procedure too complicate for not skilled people on these issues.		

NEANIAS A2.2 ATMO-SEISM Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Alekos Falagas alek.falagas@gmail.com , Makis Douskos mdouskos@gmail.com
Module Name:	ATMO-SEISM	Software Designed date:	11-2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Elena Russo e.russo11@campus.unimib.it
Dependencies:	-	Date of Execution:	28/11/2020
Test Requirements	internet access		
Service access/download	Service: http://atmo-seism.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0010		
Test Description	Login and uploading of a data set related to radon measurements and earthquake data		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Open Service and login	A successful login with NEANIAS SSO Identity provider to the service	OK	
2 Upload data to Jupyter Hub	Data successfully uploaded to the server	OK	
Test result	Login and uploading of datasets related to earthquake data and gas measurements have been concluded successfully, both csv and Excel files		

Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0011		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (.csv files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	Fail	I have not been able to proceed further.
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes		
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated		
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console		
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined		

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Test result	Failed to proceed after step 1.		
Test Case#	TEST-ATMO-SEISM-0012		
Test Description	Open jupyter notebook example and process the uploaded data (xlsx files)		
Preconditions	Previous test complete		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 Import python packages	Successful import	Fail	I have not been able to proceed further.
2 Open data with pandas	Reading data as pandas dataframes		
3 Preprocess data	Clear pandas dataframes from NAN values and coordinates are also validated		
4 Modelling	A prediction function and a R2 score is printed in console		
5 Plotting	A series of plots regarding the gas measurements and earthquake measurements combined		
Test result	Failed to proceed after step 1.		

NEANIAS A3 ATMO-4CAST Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Lúis Coimbra lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Module Name:	ATMO-4CAST	Software Designed date:	December 2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Ricardo Jorge
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	9 th December 2020
Test Requirements	Internet connection. Input data available in Google Drive folder: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1mABEZITsXioXl3-CWvoeAifS-cV9_37q		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-4cast.dev.neanias.eu Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001		
Test Description	Generate a simulation by uploading input data and visualise results		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged in.	Pass	Logged in successfully with my personal Google account
Navigate to new study page	New study page with a description of the inputs and a radio button form.	Pass	The webpage appears and I can download the sample files successfully
Select "using GRIB file data and standard WRF configuration files" radio button and click "Next"	A new form is displayed with fields for a name, description, GRIB data files, Vtable file, WPS configuration file and WRF configuration file.	Pass	Everything appears and it is clear the number of files I need to upload.
Submit test files	Simulation has been created and its details are now being displayed. The input files are available to be downloaded.	Pass	It was not very clear that I had to upload multiple files for GRIB2 data, although the form allows for multiple selection. I can download the files again but it is not very useful since I cannot open them / understand its content.
Navigate to past studies listing	Table with past studies listing user's simulation and their status.	Pass	Got there easily via the sidebar and saw the "Running status" on my

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

			experiment. It would be nice to get an estimation of time or percentage of amount of work left for the service.
When finished (should take about 15 minutes), download any output file	The following output files are present: 2 PDF files, 9 JSON files and 9 files with no extension visible.	Pass	I can download and see the output files and the charts render quite nicely. Maybe we can see the results in the web page directly instead of the files?
Test Case result	Pass		
General Comments	In general, the flow is understandable and all the steps have been executed successfully. However, it is a bit slow and requires some expertise/knowledge to understand the purpose of each file that the service takes as input. It is also not clear where I can get other samples or examples, it would be nice to have alternatives for data upload like open data about weather and atmospheric conditions. The test study does not include a timestamp, it would be nice to see when I ran each study.		

NEANIAS A3 ATMO-4CAST Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Luís Coimbra lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Module Name:	ATMO-4CAST	Software Designed date:	December 2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Alexandre Pascoal
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	11/Dec/2020
Test Requirements	Internet connection. Input data available in Google Drive folder: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1mABEZITsXioXl3-CWvoeAiFs-cV9_37q		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-4cast.dev.neanias.eu Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001		
Test Description	Generate a simulation by uploading input data and visualise results		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged in.	Pass	After the 1 st login it is unable to change the authentication (ex. Use the acc1, logout and use acc2)
Navigate to new study page	New study page with a description of the inputs and a radio button form.	Pass	
Select "using GRIB file data and standard WRF configuration files" radio button and click "Next"	A new form is displayed with fields for a name, description, GRIB data files, Vtable file, WPS configuration file and WRF configuration file.	Pass	
Submit test files	Simulation has been created and its details are now being displayed. The input files are available to be downloaded.	Pass	I am able to select any type of file, is not filtering the extensions, should list the files selected in the field GRIB1 / GRIB2 Data.
Navigate to past studies listing	Table with past studies listing user's simulation and their status.	Pass	
When finished (should take about 15 minutes), download any output file	The following output files are present: 2 PDF files, 9 JSON files and 9 files with no extension visible.	Pass	
Test Case result	Pass		

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General Comments	The main functionality is working as expected
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Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Luís Coimbra lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Module Name:	ATMO-4CAST	Software Designed date:	December 2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Rogério Silva
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	11 December 2020
Test Requirements	Internet connection. Input data available in Google Drive folder: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1mABEZITsXioXl3-CWvoeAIFs-cV9_37q		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-4cast.dev.neanias.eu Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001		
Test Description	Generate a simulation by uploading input data and visualise results		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged in	Pass	OK
Navigate to new study page	New study page with a description of the inputs and a radio button form.	Pass	OK
Select "using GRIB file data and standard WRF configuration files" radio button and click "Next"	A new form is displayed with fields for a name, description, GRIB data files, Vtable file, WPS configuration file and WRF configuration file.	Pass	OK
Submit test files	Simulation has been created and its details are now being displayed. The input files are available to be downloaded.	Pass	Takes a while to upload, may be related to my network connection. Nevertheless, a visual indication of the upload progress would be good.
Navigate to past studies listing	Table with past studies listing user's simulation and their status.	Pass	OK
When finished (should take about 15 minutes), download any output file	The following output files are present: 2 PDF files, 9 JSON files and 9 files with no extension visible.	Pass	OK

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Test Case result	Pass
General Comments	

NEANIAS A3 ATMO-4CAST Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Luís Coimbra lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Module Name:	ATMO-4CAST	Software Designed date:	December 2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Francisco Cardoso
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	11-12-2020
Test Requirements	Internet connection. Input data available in Google Drive folder: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1mABEZITsXioXl3-CWvoeAIFs-cv9_37q		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-4cast.dev.neanias.eu Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001		
Test Description	Generate a simulation by uploading input data and visualise results		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged in	Pass	
Navigate to new study page	New study page with a description of the inputs and a radio button form.	Pass	
Select "using GRIB file data and standard WRF configuration files" radio button and click "Next"	A new form is displayed with fields for a name, description, GRIB data files, Vtable file, WPS configuration file and WRF configuration file.	Pass	
Submit test files	Simulation has been created and its details are now being displayed. The input files are available to be downloaded.	Pass	Information about what's going on (In queue) should be more detailed
Navigate to past studies listing	Table with past studies listing user's simulation and their status.	Pass	
When finished (should take about 15 minutes), download any output file	The following output files are present: 2 PDF files, 9 JSON files and 9 files with no extension visible.	Pass	
Test Case result	Pass		
General Comments			

NEANIAS A3 ATMO-4CAST Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Luís Coimbra lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Module Name:	ATMO-4CAST	Software Designed date:	December 2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Fabiola Freitas
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	14/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet connection. Input data available in Google Drive folder: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1mABEZITsXioXl3-CWvoeAIFs-cV9_37q		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-4cast.dev.neanias.eu Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001		
Test Description	Generate a simulation by uploading input data and visualise results		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged in	Pass	Logged in with Google account, couldn't do it with only username and password, which for me would be preferable
Navigate to new study page	New study page with a description of the inputs and a radio button form.	Pass	
Select "using GRIB file data and standard WRF configuration files" radio button and click "Next"	A new form is displayed with fields for a name, description, GRIB data files, Vtable file, WPS configuration file and WRF configuration file.	Pass	It is weird to have to select the only option available
Submit test files	Simulation has been created and its details are now being displayed. The input files are available to be downloaded.	Pass	After submitting the files, Chrome sent out a warning stating that the connection might not be secure. It took a long time to run, and provided no feedback about the current status of the process.
Navigate to past studies listing	Table with past studies listing user's simulation and their status.	Pass	

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

When finished (should take about 15 minutes), download any output file	The following output files are present: 2 PDF files, 9 JSON files and 9 files with no extension visible.	Pass	
Test Case result	Pass		
General Comments	In general, it works! It might be a bit hard to manipulate what is going on with such complicated configuration files though. While it might be hard to avoid, given the nature of the service, all these input and output files makes it feel a bit disorganized. Would prefer something more straight forward.		

NEANIAS A3 ATMO-4CAST Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS Atmospheric Thematic Services	Software Designed by:	Lúis Coimbra lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Module Name:	ATMO-4CAST	Software Designed date:	December 2020
Release Version:	1.0	Test Executed by:	Carlos Cortinhas
Dependencies:	None	Date of Execution:	14-12-2020
Test Requirements	Internet connection. Input data available in Google Drive folder: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1mABEZITsXioXl3-CWvoeAIFs-cV9_37q		
Service access/download	Service access: https://atmo-4cast.dev.neanias.eu Service documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case#	UC-ATMO-4CAST-0001		
Test Description	Generate a simulation by uploading input data and visualise results		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Log in	User logged in.	Pass	
Navigate to new study page	New study page with a description of the inputs and a radio button form.	Pass	
Select "using GRIB file data and standard WRF configuration files" radio button and click "Next"	A new form is displayed with fields for a name, description, GRIB data files, Vtable file, WPS configuration file and WRF configuration file.	Pass	Only one radio button and its unselected, makes no sense if only one
Submit test files	Simulation has been created and its details are now being displayed. The input files are available to be downloaded.	Pass	

3.4 Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services (Release #1)

Navigate to past studies listing	Table with past studies listing user's simulation and their status.	Pass	
When finished (should take about 15 minutes), download any output file	The following output files are present: 2 PDF files, 9 JSON files and 9 files with no extension visible.	Pass	
Test Case result	Pass		
General Comments			